

DEVELOPMENT OF A LOW SUGAR PROTEIN BAR

development and market introduction of

**AbsoRice New Generation bar with high protein and fiber content, lactose- and
gluten-free**

for a research and development project.

2019

Absorice Hungary Kft.

Reviewed by Tamas Kiss, MSc

Table of Contents

I.	Summary	p. 3
II.	Major Technical Parameters	p. 5
II / a.	Double Chocolate Brownie - an all time favorite	p. 6
II / b.	Vanilla - Cookies flavor - a fine balance	p. 9
II / c.	Strawberry flavor - a challenging one	p. 12
III.	Logistics	p. 15
IV.	Design	p. 16

I. Summary

In connection with our research and development project, we undertook the creation of a delicious, filling, high protein and fiber content, free of animal ingredients, affordable, lactose and gluten free, with a low insulin response, which we successfully completed with the help of the grant.

We have created a product line that matches the market potential of the classic chocolate bars made of sugar, palm oil, milk powder and cocoa, and which rides on the healthy lifestyle trend that has already appeared. We put sweets on the shelves that are delicious, filling and nourish and energize the body instead of a "sugar coma".

The name of the products is AbsoBAR Zero, a vegetable protein bar, which refers to the low sugar content (no added sugar), allergen-free - more precisely, gluten- and lactose-free. We made them in three flavors as promised, but we created a recipe platform that can be flavored to create additional flavors.

We prepared the product with chocolate and dipping paste coatings, and based on the developed recipe, we can also offer the slices to business customers under a different brand name in different sizes, which further increases the business potential. In the case of our own-brand AbsoBAR Zero bars, we finally decided on a dipping coating, because according to tests, chocolate only works well in a temperate environment during its entire product life. Since this cannot be ensured in all cases, and the coating is technologically more robust, we decided on a more resistant solution.

The product's high fiber content is ensured by liquid fibers, fructo-oligosaccharide and isomalto-oligosaccharide, which are made from chicory fiber and corn. Their prebiotic effect, low energy content and long-term absorption into the bloodstream endows our slices with positive physiological effects.

The development of bars based on rice and pea protein is a unique field, we have not seen such a product on the market at the European level, we are targeting this gap with the developed slices and the knowledge accumulated during research and development.

Bringing the product to the market is fully prepared on the marketing, distribution and business development side, sales can even start immediately. The prototypes have been

manufactured, and we have achieved the expected taste, consistency and fashionable look desirable for the target group.

As a team dedicated to developing an exceptional vegan protein bar, we embarked on a meticulous journey, beginning with conceptualization and market research. Our initial focus was on identifying our target market and understanding their unique needs and preferences. We sought to create a product that not only met the nutritional requirements of our health-conscious, plant-based consumers but also stood out in a crowded marketplace. Through extensive market analysis, we defined the optimal nutritional profile for our bar, balancing high protein content with the right levels of carbohydrates, fats, and additional functional benefits like fiber and vitamins. We delved into the competitive landscape, identifying gaps and opportunities to craft a unique selling proposition that would set our bar apart.

With a clear concept in mind, we moved to ingredient selection and formulation. We rigorously explored various plant-based protein sources, including pea, soy, rice, and hemp, each bringing distinct advantages and challenges. Our goal was to blend these proteins to ensure a complete amino acid profile, addressing the inherent limitations of individual plant proteins. Beyond proteins, we carefully selected ingredients that would enhance the bar's taste, texture, and nutritional value. We focused on natural sweeteners, fibers, and fats that complemented the protein blend. Finding suitable binding agents was crucial; we opted for plant-based options like syrups and nut butters to ensure our bars held together well without being overly sticky or dry. Throughout this stage, our team conducted extensive trials and testing, fine-tuning the recipe to achieve the perfect balance of flavor, texture, and nutritional content.

In the product development and testing phase, we transitioned from small-scale kitchen experiments to lab size, then factory size tests and eventually full-scale production. This phase required us to refine our manufacturing processes meticulously, ensuring consistency and quality across large batches. We conducted rigorous testing to evaluate the bar's texture, taste, and nutritional profile, making adjustments as needed to align with our high standards. Shelf-life testing was essential; we worked to determine how long our bars could be stored while maintaining their quality and safety. Packaging development was another critical focus, as we sought solutions that protected the bars from environmental factors and aligned with our commitment to sustainability. We selected packaging that was both functional and aligned with our brand's values. Finally, we navigated the regulatory landscape to ensure full compliance with food safety and labeling requirements. Each of these steps culminated in a product that we were proud to bring to market—a vegan protein bar designed to exceed consumer expectations and thrive in a competitive space.

II. Major Technical Parameters

Developing vegan protein bars presents a myriad of challenges, primarily stemming from the unique characteristics and limitations of plant-based ingredients. One of the foremost difficulties is sourcing high-quality, affordable plant proteins that offer a complete amino acid profile comparable to animal proteins. Many plant proteins lack one or more essential amino acids, necessitating careful formulation to achieve nutritional balance. Moreover, these proteins often have strong, distinctive flavors and a gritty or chalky texture that require significant effort to mask or improve. Finding effective vegan binding agents, like dates or nut butters, instead of traditional options like honey or gelatin, further complicates the process as they can significantly alter the bar's texture and flavor profile.

Additionally, maintaining shelf stability without preservatives while ensuring the bars remain safe and high-quality over time is a significant technological challenge. Balancing the need for adequate protein, carbohydrates, fats, and micronutrients within vegan dietary restrictions demands meticulous formulation. The use of common allergens like nuts and soy introduces further complexities, making it difficult to produce bars that are safe and appealing to a broad audience. Processing techniques also play a crucial role, as some plant proteins require specialized methods to enhance their solubility and integration into the bar matrix without compromising their nutritional value. Cost is another critical factor; high-quality vegan protein sources can be expensive, making it challenging to keep the product competitively priced.

Beyond these technical aspects, there are additional considerations such as maintaining flavor consistency across batches, ensuring sustainable and ethical ingredient sourcing, and complying with regulatory standards for vegan certification and food safety. Meeting consumer expectations for clean label products without artificial additives while delivering on taste, texture, and nutritional value adds another layer of complexity. Innovations in flavor development are essential to keep the product appealing amidst growing market competition. Moreover, achieving the right moisture balance to prevent the bars from being too dry or sticky is critical, and selecting appropriate packaging that preserves quality and aligns with sustainability goals is equally important. The interplay of these factors underscores the significant challenges in creating a successful vegan protein bar.

Designing our vegan protein bar was a creative and collaborative endeavor, deeply rooted in our commitment to meet consumer needs and inspired by trends in health and sustainability. From the outset, our vision was to create a product that seamlessly combined nutrition, flavor, and convenience while upholding the highest ethical standards. Our inspiration drew heavily from the

growing demand for plant-based, clean-label foods. We wanted our bar to resonate with health-conscious consumers who are increasingly mindful of what they eat and how it impacts both their bodies and the planet. Our design process was driven by the desire to provide a wholesome, satisfying snack that people could enjoy anytime, anywhere, without compromising their dietary choices or values.

In shaping the product, we drew inspiration from the rich diversity of natural ingredients available in the plant-based world. We sought to capture the essence of these ingredients, emphasizing their natural flavors and textures. This approach guided us to experiment with a variety of nuts, seeds, fruits, and whole grains, each contributing unique taste profiles and nutritional benefits. We were particularly inspired by the versatility of ingredients like dates, which provided a natural sweetness and served as an excellent binding agent, and nuts, which offered crunch and a rich source of healthy fats. Our flavor combinations aimed to reflect the harmony of these elements, whether it was a nutty, savory blend or a sweet, fruity mix, always ensuring that the end product was as enjoyable to eat as it was beneficial to health.

Sustainability was another key pillar in our product design philosophy. We wanted our protein bar to not only be good for consumers but also for the environment. This commitment influenced our choice of ingredients, favoring those that were sustainably sourced and minimally processed. We were inspired by the idea of creating a product that left a lighter footprint on the earth, from the farm to the shelf. This ethos extended to our packaging design as well. We opted for materials that were recyclable or biodegradable, aligning with our goal of reducing waste and promoting environmental stewardship. Throughout the design process, we remained focused on our core values—health, taste, convenience, and sustainability—ensuring that every aspect of our vegan protein bar reflected these principles.

The main parameters of the product, which are relevant from the point of view of the food industry, are the following.

II / a. Double Chocolate Brownie - an all time favorite

Ingredients:

AbsoRice protein mixture (pea protein isolate, rice protein concentrate), isomaltoligosaccharide*, fructo-oligosaccharide, cocoa coating mass with sweetener 15% [sweetener: maltitol, fully hydrogenated vegetable fat (palm kernel), low-fat cocoa powder 15%, emulsifiers (sunflower lecithin, polyglycerin-polyricinoleate), aroma], rapeseed oil, emulsifier: soy lecithin,

cocoa powder 6%, chocolate pieces 2.5% (sugar, cocoa mass, cocoa butter, emulsifier: soy lecithin, natural aroma), humectant: glycerin, aroma, thickener: carboxymethyl -cellulose, antioxidant: rosemary extract, sweetener: steviol glycosides

*Isomalto-oligosaccharide is a source of glucose.

The product is GMO-free, lactose-free, gluten-free, and free of animal ingredients.

Net weight of the product: **40 g**

Production method:

1. Cleaning and drying of plant equipment and contact surfaces.
2. Measuring and mixing of the liquid phase and the powder phase.
3. Forming a body from the mass.
4. Application of chocolate coating.
5. Frosting the chocolate coating.
6. Packaging in foil, airtight seal.

Technology description:

Before starting the measurement, the rooms used during production are cleaned and dried with water, as well as the surfaces in contact with the product are completely cleaned and dried with water. The tested ingredients are measured according to the recipe. The liquid phase is mixed with the powder phase and kneaded into a homogeneous mass in the suitable mixing equipment. From the mass, the extrusion roller shapes the body of the slice, and then the dipping machine applies the chocolate coating to the body. The coated slice solidifies in the cooling tunnel. The finished slice is wrapped in metallized foil by the packaging machine and sealed airtight. During the process, the product must not come into contact with water.

Packaging:

Material specification	Packaging method	Number of products per unit
20BOPP/METBOPP multi-layer metallized foil	Automated packaging from flat foil	1 pc

Quality characteristics of the bar:

Composition characteristics (physical, chemical, etc. characteristics):

A bar coated with cocoa coating mass, with a mass-like body

Sensory characteristics:

Parameter	Properties
Appearance	coated bar
Color	dark brown body and dark brown coating
Taste	characteristic chocolate flavor
Scent	characteristic chocolate scent

Average nutritional values:

a) list and amount of nutrients per 100 g and one portion (40 g):

Energy:	1673 kJ/400 kcal	669 kJ/160 kcal
Fat:	21,2 g	8,5 g
Of which saturated fats:	8,9 g	3,6 g
Carbohydrates:	17,4 g	7,0 g
Of which sugars:	4,7 g	1,9 g
Of which polyols:	8,1 g	3,2 g
Fiber:	23,3 g	9,3 g
Protein:	26,6 g	10,7 g
Salt:	0,50 g	0,20 g

Shelf life:

12 months from production, in unopened packaging.

To be consumed within 1 day after opening.

Storage conditions: In a dry, cool place, protected from radiant heat and light.

Food labeling:

57/2010. (V.7.) According to the FVM decree. EC Regulation 1924/2006 on nutritional and health claims related to food.

Gluten-free, lactose-free, vegan: Does not contain ingredients of animal origin, ingredients containing gluten or ingredients containing lactose.

During the production steps, the introduction of gluten, lactose and other potential cross-contamination is excluded with a quality-assured production process.

Excessive consumption may have a laxative effect.

II / b. Vanilla - Cookies flavor - a fine balance

Ingredients:

AbsoRice protein mixture (pea protein isolate, rice protein concentrate), fructo-oligosaccharide, isomalto-oligosaccharide*, cocoa coating mass with sweetener 15% [sweetener (maltitol), fully hydrogenated vegetable fat (palm kernel), low-fat cocoa powder 15%, emulsifiers (sunflower lecithin , polyglycerin-polyricinoleate), aroma], rapeseed oil, emulsifier: soy lecithin, gluten-free biscuit pieces 3.4% [rice flour, sweetener (maltitol), corn starch, palm oil, cocoa powder, corn flour, inulin, sunflower oil, bulking agent: sodium carbonates, thickener : xanthan gum, salt, emulsifier: sunflower lecithin], humectant: glycerin, aroma, thickener: carboxymethyl cellulose, antioxidant: rosemary extract, sweetener: steviol glycosides.

The product is GMO-free, lactose-free, gluten-free, and free of animal ingredients.

Net weight of the product: **40 g**

Production method:

1. Cleaning and drying of plant equipment and contact surfaces.
2. Measuring and mixing of the liquid phase and the powder phase.
3. Forming a body from the mass.
4. Application of chocolate coating.
5. Frosting the chocolate coating.
6. Packaging in foil, airtight seal.

Technology description:

Before starting the production, the rooms used during production are cleaned and dried with water, as well as the surfaces in contact with the product are completely cleaned and dried with water. The tested ingredients are measured according to the recipe. The liquid phase is mixed with the powder phase and kneaded into a homogeneous mass in the suitable mixing equipment. From the mass, the extrusion roller shapes the body of the slice, and then the dipping machine applies the chocolate coating to the body. The coated slice solidifies in the cooling tunnel. The finished slice is wrapped in metallized foil by the packaging machine and sealed airtight. During the process, the product must not come into contact with water.

Packaging:

Material specification	Packaging method	Number of products per unit
20BOPP/METBOPP multi-layer metallized foil	Automated packaging from flat foil	1 pc

Quality characteristics of the bar:

Composition characteristics (physical, chemical, etc. characteristics):

A bar coated with cocoa coating mass, with a mass-like body

Sensory characteristics:

Parameter	Property
Appearance	coated bar
Color	pale beige body and dark brown coating
Taste	characteristic vanilla flavor
Scent	characteristic vanilla scent

Average nutritional values:

- a) list and amount of nutrients per 100 g and one portion (40 g):

Energy:	1645 kJ/393 kcal	658 kJ/157 kcal
Fat:	19,6 g	7,9 g
Of which saturated fats:	8,0 g	3,2 g
Carbohydrates:	19,2 g	7,7 g
Of which sugars:	3,9 g	1,6 g
Of which polyols:	8,5 g	3,4 g
Fiber:	23,5 g	9,4 g
Protein:	26,6 g	10,6 g
Salt:	0,58 g	0,23 g

Shelf life:

12 months from production, in unopened packaging.

To be consumed within 1 day after opening.

Storage conditions: In a dry, cool place, protected from radiant heat and light.

Food labeling:

57/2010. (V.7.) According to the FVM decree. EC Regulation 1924/2006 on nutritional and health claims related to food.

Gluten-free, lactose-free, vegan: Does not contain ingredients of animal origin, ingredients containing gluten or ingredients containing lactose.

During the production steps, the introduction of gluten, lactose and other potential cross-contamination is excluded with a quality-assured production process.

Excessive consumption may have a laxative effect.

II / c. Strawberry flavor - a challenging one

Ingredients:

AbsoRice protein mixture (pea protein isolate, rice protein concentrate), isomalto-oligosaccharide*, fructo-oligosaccharide, cocoa coating mass with sweetener 15% [sweetener (maltitol), fully hydrogenated vegetable fat (palm kernel), low-fat cocoa powder 15%, emulsifiers (sunflower lecithin , polyglycerin-polyricinoleate), aroma], rapeseed oil, emulsifier: soy lecithin, humectant: glycerin, beetroot extract, freeze-dried strawberry pieces 1%, aroma, thickener: carboxymethylcellulose, antioxidant: rosemary extract, sweetener: steviol glycosides.

The product is GMO-free, lactose-free, gluten-free, and free of animal ingredients.

Net weight of the product: **40 g**

Production method:

1. Cleaning and drying of plant equipment and contact surfaces.
2. Measuring and mixing of the liquid phase and the powder phase.
3. Forming a body from the mass.
4. Application of chocolate coating.
5. Frosting the chocolate coating.
6. Packaging in foil, airtight seal.

Technology description:

Before starting the production, the rooms used during production are cleaned and dried with water, as well as the surfaces in contact with the product are completely cleaned and dried with water. The tested ingredients are measured according to the recipe. The liquid phase is mixed with the powder phase and kneaded into a homogeneous mass in the suitable mixing equipment. From the mass, the extrusion roller shapes the body of the slice, and then the dipping machine applies the chocolate coating to the body. The coated slice solidifies in the cooling tunnel. The finished slice is wrapped in metallized foil by the packaging machine and sealed airtight. During the process, the product must not come into contact with water.

Packaging:

Material specification	Packaging method	Number of products per unit
20BOPP/METBOPP multi-layer metallized foil	Automated packaging from flat foil	1 pc

Quality characteristics of the bar:

Composition characteristics (physical, chemical, etc. characteristics):

A bar coated with cocoa coating mass, with a mass-like body

Sensory characteristics:

Parameter	Properties
Appearance	coated bar
Color	pink body and dark brown coating
Taste	characteristic strawberry flavor
Scent	characteristic strawberry scent

Average nutritional values:

a) list and amount of nutrients per 100 g and one portion (40 g):

Energy:	1636 kJ/391 kcal	654 kJ/156 kcal
Fat:	20,2 g	8,1 g
Of which saturated fats:	7,8 g	3,1 g
Carbohydrates:	18,2 g	7,3 g
Of which sugars:	4,2 g	1,7 g
Of which polyols:	8,1 g	3,2 g
Fiber:	23,5 g	9,4 g
Protein:	25,7 g	10,3 g
Salt:	0,52 g	0,21 g

Shelf life:

12 months from production, in unopened packaging.

To be consumed within 1 day after opening.

Storage conditions: In a dry, cool place, protected from radiant heat and light.

Food labeling:

57/2010. (V.7.) According to the FVM decree. EC Regulation 1924/2006 on nutritional and health claims related to food.

Gluten-free, lactose-free, vegan: Does not contain ingredients of animal origin, ingredients containing gluten or ingredients containing lactose.

During the production steps, the introduction of gluten, lactose and other potential cross-contamination is excluded with a quality-assured production process.

Excessive consumption may have a laxative effect.

III. Logistics

The table below outlines the collected best practices and provides reasonable ratios considering the logistical aspects of the development.

Quality retention time in days	365
Customs tariff number	21069092
Individual package net weight g	40
Individual package gross weight g	41
Collection unit net weight kg	0.96
Collection unit gross weight kg	1.00
Packaging foil weight g / 1pc	1.00
Packaging weight g / 1pc	40.00
Packaging collection # weight g / 1pc	580.00
Packaging pallet weight g / 1pc	2000.00
Net weight of 1 pallet product kg	345.6 kg
Gross weight of 1 pallet product kg	386.04 kg
PCS / display (bar only)	24.00
Collection unit (pc/#)	288
Vendor / Collector# (bar only)	12
Collector # / pallet line	6
Cardboard line / pallet	5
Collector # / pallet	30
PC / pallet	8640 db
unit size (core*width*depth) mm	15*150*45
Delivery box dimensions mm (length*width*core)	175*155*80
Collection box dimensions (length*width*core) mm	370*335*250
(Collection box height)	250
1 Total height of the goods on the pallet in cm (without pallet)	125 cm
1 Total height of the goods on the pallet in cm (with pallet)	139 cm

Logistics - considering all aspects

IV. Design

In designing the visual identity of our vegan protein bars, we aimed to create packaging that not only stands out on the shelves but also communicates the core values of our brand. The color green became a cornerstone of our graphic design, symbolizing the natural, plant-based essence of our product. Green is often associated with health, vitality, and sustainability, making it the perfect choice to represent our commitment to vegan and eco-friendly practices. We extended this color theme across all our flavors, ensuring a cohesive and recognizable brand image. Each flavor variant is distinguished by subtle shades and accents, maintaining visual consistency while allowing for differentiation.

The design of the products was completed as a result of the analysis of the target group, to serve the customer's key parameters as defined in the plan. According to its characteristics, it is vegan, i.e. green, reminiscent of the rice fields from which the main ingredient is rice protein, i.e. striped, free of all allergens, i.e. clean.

Our design also incorporates flowing wave patterns that evoke the lush, undulating landscapes of rice fields on hills. These waves symbolize growth, harmony, and the natural cycle of life, resonating with our dedication to providing wholesome, plant-based nutrition. The gentle curves and fluid lines of the waves create a sense of movement and energy, reflecting the dynamic and nourishing nature of our protein bars. This imagery is not just aesthetically pleasing but also meaningful, as it connects the product to its natural roots and the earth's bounty. By integrating these elements, we aimed to craft packaging that tells a story of purity and the connection between nature and nourishment.

Consistency was paramount in our graphic design strategy. We wanted each flavor of our protein bars to feel part of a unified family while highlighting its unique attributes. To achieve this, we applied the green color palette and wave motifs uniformly across all our products. Each flavor's specific ingredients are subtly highlighted with complementary colors and imagery, providing clear differentiation while maintaining overall brand harmony. This approach ensures that whether a customer chooses our almond, berry, or chocolate variant, they immediately recognize it as part of our brand's wholesome, vegan offering. Our design philosophy is reflected in every detail, aiming to create a visually appealing and cohesive product line that appeals to health-conscious consumers and underscores our commitment to quality and sustainability.

It shows the taste of the tasty protein bar in pictorial form, this is the only and at the same time the most striking information. The final result is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 1 – AbsoBAR Double Chocolate Brownie 40g protein bars in the 24 x 40g display box